

ISic4396

Dedication to Isis

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

column

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Fragment (a) excavated in 2008 in the Parco archeologico di Lilibeo, Area B, saggio VI; fragment (b) found in Marsala, September 1903 in the 'terre di Rocco Trapani, in prossimita' di Gill e la Salinella' (i.e. a few hundred metres from fr.a).

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi, inventory 8285

Physical Description

2 joining fragments of a small white limestone column

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Text

1. [Ἰσιδι] μυριωνύ
2. [μωθ]εἰ μέγιστη
3. []τοι Ῥουφεί
4. [νου] διὰ Εὐδαίμ
5. [ονος] ἐπιτρόπου
6. τοῦτο τὸ βῆμα
7. [εὐ]χὴν ἀπέ[δωκαν]
8. ἐπ' ἀγαθ[ῶ]

Apparatus

Text of Brugnone 2015

Translation (en)

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 161701

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 85

Brugnone, A. 2015. La dedica a Iside da Lilibeo. *Mare Internum. Archeologia e culture del Mediterraneo*. 7: 99-108. At 103-104 fig.1, 10, 11

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Photo R.J.A. Wilson